

Enhancing Understanding and Performance in Competency-Based Education: A Visual Management Approach

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Abstract

The competency-based education model has gained prominence in Brazil in recent decades, largely due to the actions of the Ministry of Education, which replaced the old higher education model based on minimum curricula with the National Curricular Guidelines for Higher Education (DNC). This transition presents challenges, particularly in terms of visually managing the new system, crucial for students to understand its structure and track their performance. This work proposes the application of visual management in competency-based education, aiming to facilitate understanding of the curriculum structure and performance tracking by competencies throughout the course, as opposed to focusing solely on disciplines. To achieve this, methodologies such as knowledge management and agile practices were adopted, along with tools such as brainstorming and value proposition canvas. The solution was implemented using the virtual platform Frigma, resulting in positive outcomes evaluated with stakeholders at a Brazilian higher education institution, with significant improvements in performance indicators. It is concluded, therefore, that the adoption of visual tools represents an effective approach to enhancing students' understanding of the competency-based education model.

Keywords: Competency-based education; Visual management; Curriculum structure; Performance tracking.

1 Introduction

Competence, originally a term rooted in legal discourse, has evolved significantly over time. Initially denoting the authority of a public body to adjudicate certain matters, its scope broadened as scholars like Harvard University psychologist David C. McClelland redefined it. McClelland (1973) advocated for assessments measuring not just cognitive abilities but also skills and personality traits. This led to a broader understanding of competence as the amalgamation of knowledge, skills, and attitudes (KSA). Building upon this, Le Boterf (1995) defined competence as the capability to deploy KSA resources to tackle complex challenges.

Today, the concept of competence finds application across diverse domains, from professional arenas to educational realms. It signifies a shift from merely possessing knowledge to embodying a multifaceted skill set. This shift underpins competency-based education, a contemporary pedagogical model geared towards cultivating holistic professional capabilities rather than rote content absorption (Lourenço, Nara, Gonçalves, & Canciglieri, 2023; Tardio, Schaefer, Gonçalves, & Nara, 2023; Tardio, Schaefer, Nara, Gonçalves, Dias, Benitez, & Castro e Silva, 2023).

The Pontifical Catholic University of Paraná (PUCPR), situated in Brazil, stands at the forefront of this educational paradigm shift, pioneering the adoption of competency-based models. However, this transition has not been without hurdles. One notable challenge lies in effectively communicating the model's intricacies to students, particularly concerning performance indicators and learning trajectories.

Thus, this study endeavors to address this challenge by implementing visual management strategies within PUCPR's competency-based education framework. Focusing on the Engineering programs, particularly Production Engineering and Control and Automation Engineering, this initiative aims to enhance students'

comprehension of the teaching structure and facilitate visualization of their competency progression throughout their academic journey. The choice of Engineering programs is strategic, aligning with the stringent competency standards set by international accreditation bodies like the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET). By enhancing the transparency and accessibility of competency-based education, this research seeks to contribute to the broader adoption and efficacy of this educational model in Brazil (ABET, 2021). In light of this context, the central research question emerges: Can visual management strategies make the competency-based education model more accessible and comprehensible for PUCPR programs? This study seeks to not only answer this question but also to implement and validate practical solutions aimed at empowering students within the competency-based education framework.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is the area aimed at managing the knowledge held by an organization, whether it is stored in data or present in employees. This type of management has gained much more strength in recent decades, due to the incredible increase in computational capacity and data availability. Thus, better utilization of this resource can offer significant strategic advantages for organizations (Faria, Tulik, & Gonçalves, 2019).

One way to exercise information management within the organization is through data analysis, as this can provide a greater situational awareness of the context faced. According to Sordi (2015), data is collections of relevant evidence about an observed fact. That is, they are a set of elements about a particular event, and observing a single piece of data is not as effective. Therefore, it is the analysis of the data, the extraction of information from the sets of data obtained from a particular fact. Sinclair (2017) outlines data analysis in a set of three stages: (i) Data preparation: This stage involves identifying and extracting data in its native form, which can be spreadsheets or databases (Vianna, Gonçalves, Dias, & Nara, 2024). They are normalized, a process in which different data is standardized, structured, and processed to be compatible with data analysis. And they are loaded into the database; (ii) Analysis: In this stage, mathematical equations are applied to extract information from the stored data (Junior, & Gonçalves, 2019). (iii) Communicating results: This stage involves using business intelligence tools to express the results and information obtained from data analysis (Gonçalves, Antunes, & Zanellato, 2023).

2.2 Visual Management

In today's data-driven landscape, organizations are increasingly recognizing the critical importance of leveraging knowledge assets, harnessing data insights, and fostering transparent communication. The convergence of Knowledge Management (KM), Data Analysis, and Visual Management represents a powerful synergy, enabling organizations to optimize decision-making processes, enhance strategic planning, and drive sustainable growth.

Data Analysis encompasses the systematic exploration, interpretation, and visualization of data to extract actionable insights and inform decision-making processes. Leveraging advanced analytics techniques, organizations can uncover hidden patterns, trends, and correlations within their datasets, enabling them to derive valuable business intelligence and strategic foresight. From descriptive analytics for retrospective analysis to predictive analytics for forecasting future trends, data analysis empowers organizations to make informed decisions and drive performance optimization across various functional domains (Gonçalves, Machado, Nara, Dias, & Vaz, 2023).

Visual Management involves the strategic use of visual aids, such as charts, graphs, dashboards, and infographics, to communicate complex information in a clear, concise, and intuitive manner. By transforming raw data into visually engaging representations, organizations can enhance comprehension, facilitate knowledge sharing, and promote alignment towards common objectives. Through visual storytelling and interactive data visualization, stakeholders can gain deeper insights into organizational performance metrics, project milestones, and strategic initiatives, fostering greater transparency and accountability (Gonçalves, Pamplona, Nara, & Dias, 2023).

In essence, the integration of Knowledge Management, Data Analysis, and Visual Management represents a holistic approach to information management and decision support. By harnessing the collective wisdom of employees, unlocking actionable insights from data, and communicating findings through compelling visualizations, organizations can enhance their capacity to adapt to change, drive innovation, and achieve sustainable competitive advantage in an increasingly complex and dynamic business environment.

3 A Visual Management Approach

3.1 Solution Planning Process

3.1.1 Problem Statement

The Production Engineering program at PUCPR, in accordance with the university's guidelines, has adopted a competency-based education system. In this system, the aim is to empower students to apply their knowledge in real-life situations, defining competence as the set of skills and values that students must acquire throughout their academic training.

To implement this system, it is necessary to map and integrate competencies into the program curriculum in order to guide the planning of activities offered throughout the curriculum.

However, students have faced some difficulty in understanding how the system works, as reported in surveys conducted by ABET with students in the final semester of the program. Specifically, there have been difficulties in understanding how the acquisition of competencies evolves throughout the program, which has not contributed to the development of interdisciplinary projects.

3.1.1.1 Problem Measurement

Initially, the problem was subjectively estimated through stakeholders' perceptions and observations of the situation, made through direct interactions.

In order to quantitatively measure this perception, indicators were developed to assess stakeholders' and students' satisfaction with the way the competency system is communicated, as well as students' level of understanding of the competency system. These indicators are obtained through surveys conducted with stakeholders.

3.1.2 Analysis of Root Cause and Possible Solutions

3.1.2.1 Root Cause Analysis

The root cause analysis was developed through the use of tools and analysis of data collected with project stakeholders.

Based on the results of the tools used, a hypothesis was raised stating that the main root cause of the problem was related to the lack of a graphical representation that would enable students to see learning in a systemic and evolutionary way. It was termed "main" because it was understood that all other causes would be

consequences of the lack of systemic vision. This hypothesis was presented to the Program Nucleus (NDE) in a meeting, where it was accepted and thus became the basis for the development of possible solutions.

3.1.2.2 Possible Solutions

For the development of solutions, brainstorming tools and a value proposition canvas were used, along with validation with stakeholders to define the best solution proposal.

The chosen proposal would consist of an interactive interface that would change according to each student's performance data. This interface would have its design and functionality based on the skill tree model used in various games. The interface would also be hosted on its own platform, regardless of the online learning platform already adopted by the institution.

After the proposal development period, a meeting was held with the stakeholders, presenting to them the proposals, their justifications, benefits, and gains. It was concluded that the proposal developed in this study was the most appropriate to address the topic.

3.2 Implementation of Visual Competency Management

3.2.1 Data Collection

The programs of Production Engineering and Control and Automation Engineering at PUCPR are certified by the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET). Because of this, these programs adopt several actions and best practices aimed at their continuous improvement and maintaining accreditation. Many of these actions are related to the establishment and monitoring of performance indicators by the students.

All data from the indicators are stored in databases in spreadsheet format using Excel software. They contain data related to the teaching structure of competencies and the performance indicators of each student. Therefore, the databases provided by the International Accreditation were used to build the graphical interface models.

3.2.2 Design Selection

The interface aims to be a visual tool to assist in understanding the competency-based education system. It enables visualizing the individual performance of each student. Therefore, the entire design construction of this tool was based on the structure and flow of teaching present in competency mapping.

The competency-based education system differs from others by structuring its teaching around the competencies learned rather than the courses/disciplines (contents). Competencies are understood as a set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that need to be mobilized to solve a specific problem. This concept is represented by programs through Learning Outcomes (LOs) and their respective levels. Each LO represents a part of the competency, which can be a small part of the knowledge, skill, or attitude that the competency aims to achieve. Therefore, each competency is formed by a chain of LOs, which over time aims to present and develop each element to the students. This development of LOs over time is expressed through the level system, which consists of three different degrees: introductory, mobilizing, and certifying. In the introductory level, there are learning outcomes that aim to introduce new knowledge to the student; the mobilizing level encompasses LOs that aim to mobilize previously learned knowledge and establish new concepts; finally, the certifying level is where the LOs are aimed at verifying if the student has internalized previous learning. Competencies, as they are not tied to specific content, can have their learning outcomes distributed across different courses/disciplines throughout the program. In addition to the level system, competencies have also been subdivided into competency elements. These divisions aim to separate what is expected of each competency into smaller parts. This entire structure can be observed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Main screen of the graphical interface.

In Figure 1, we can observe in the columns the competencies of a specific program, where each competency is divided into competency elements, and finally, in the rows, you have the program courses/disciplines (course 1, course 2, ..., course n), where each discipline has different learning outcomes (LOs) that will be evaluated per course. As mentioned earlier, each course may have LOs that contribute to different competencies of the program. The PUCPR system has defined different levels for the LOs, represented by different colours in the figure. The yellow colour signifies an introductory level LO, the orange colour represents a mobilizing level LO, and the brown colour signifies a certifying level LO. With this, it is possible to observe an evolution in the construction of competencies, where each competency has LOs of all levels and concludes with a certifying LO, typically represented per discipline, which verifies if the student has been able to acquire that competency.

For this project, the design was defined in the form of a skill tree, aiming to graphically represent all the structures and mechanisms present in the system as clearly as possible. Therefore, part of the system has its respective graphical representation. Competencies were represented as large tracks, divided into smaller tracks representing competency elements. Each track, in turn, was subdivided into Learning Outcomes, graphically represented in the form of circles. The level system was represented through the colours on the edges of the circles, while the performance of the indicators was represented by the internal colours of each LO. The entire structure was organized in the form of arcs, with the radii of each arc representing the semesters, with the closer to the centre, the smaller the semester.

Next to the skills tree, a panel was developed to insert data related to each Learning Outcome. The proposal is that data such as: Course, grade, code, and the text referring to the Learning Outcome, be displayed when the user clicks on a button corresponding to the LO.

Figure 2 presents the generic interface screen, in which no button is pressed. It is possible to observe three large sections representing the specific competencies of the program. When referring to specific competencies, this includes those directly linked to the professional characteristics of engineering. The other competency pertains to common core competencies, which refer to the basic training of every engineer, a competency that was not of interest in this mapping study. Also, observable are smaller subdivisions representing the elements of competence and buttons representing the learning outcomes (LOs). The same color palette used by PUCPR was employed for its creation.

Figure 2. Main screen of the graphical interface.

Figure 2 presents a simulation of the solution for this project, using the student who authored this project as an example. It allows for visual management of the performance of each specific competency in the program. Additionally, different colours indicate the grade obtained in each learning outcome (LO). For example, a grade equal to or greater than 8.5 is shown in green, a grade equal to or less than 7 is shown in red, and grades between 7 and 8.5 are shown in yellow. In the example provided, one can quickly analyse the competencies in which the student excels and those in which improvement is needed. At the time of implementing the solution, the student was in the eighth semester, thus, the performance for the ninth and tenth semesters had not yet been assessed and are represented by the colour grey.

3.2.3 Prototyping

The implemented solution was the minimum viable product (MVP) to enable users to understand the proposed design and functionality of the system. For this purpose, the Figma prototyping platform was utilized, a tool commonly used by designers to emulate the basic functionalities of an application before its final construction. With the assistance of this tool, the basic design of the interface was developed along with the button functionalities, which displayed information on the screen when activated.

In the prototyping phase, it was necessary to develop various frames representing the screens after button presses. It was also necessary to create links between the buttons and the respective screens they lead to. This allowed us to emulate the system's functionality, demonstrating the various possible screen flows in the system's operation.

3.3 Validation of the Implemented Solution

In order to assess the acceptance of the solution by the users and identify possible improvements, evaluative forms and interviews were developed for the two audiences who would benefit from the new tool, the professors and the students. Each audience has different needs to be addressed. The students represent the main audience, aiming to offer them assistance in understanding the functioning of the competency-based education system and a graphical tool for monitoring their performance according to the competencies. For the professors, the aim is to provide an evaluative tool that can diagnose the students' performance according to the competency-based education model and not just by courses.

3.3.1 Measurement of Improvement Using Success Indicator

With the students, quantitative evaluations were also conducted in which ratings from 1 to 5 were assigned to the following topics: Understandability, usability, design, intuitiveness, and usefulness. In addition, inquiries

were made about the prior knowledge each one had regarding the functioning of the competency-based education model and how much this knowledge improved after the presentation of the tool. Out of the 23 respondents, 13 answered the objective questionnaire. The following table presents the evaluated items and their respective average ratings:

Table 1. Average scores of evaluative criteria.

Question	Average grade
How well could you understand the functioning of the competency system before the presentation with graphical representation?	2,5
How much did your knowledge about the education system improve after the presentation?	4,7
How do you assess the intelligibility of the interface? (It's how understandable the system is to the user)	4,3
How do you assess the usability of the interface? (It's how easy it is for the user to use the system to extract information)	4,6
How do you assess the design of the interface? (Refers to the organization of information, color palette, and responsiveness of the system.)	4,3
How do you assess the intuitiveness of the interface? (It's how understandable the system is to the user without needing secondary information)	3,9
How do you assess the usefulness of the interface? (It's how useful the system can be for users, beyond its primary function)	4,8

Before the solution was presented to the students, it was observed that the average obtained was below 2.5 for the questions on the form, and after implementing the solution, according to table 1, the majority of questions obtained average values above 4. This indicates that the use of a graphical tool had a significant impact on users' perception.

4 Final Considerations

Therefore, it can be observed that the application of graphical tools to the context of competency-based education model aids in improving its intelligibility. In this work, methodologies and tools were used to meet the general objective and the specific objectives. The aim was to find and identify problems and their causes through the use of tools related to the scope of agile methodologies, such as brainstorming and the value proposition canvas. To implement the solution, the Figma platform was used to build the graphical interface design. Finally, to understand the stakeholders' opinions regarding the proposed solution that was implemented, interviews and quantitative research were conducted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the project achieved its desired objective.

To scientifically validate the proposed model, a comprehensive literature review was conducted. This review revealed that there are no previous studies directly addressing this specific model in the context of competency-based engineering education. This absence of studies highlights the originality and innovation of our proposal (Gonçalves, Nara, Santos, Mateus & Amaral, 2023; Hamasaki, Gonçalves, Junior, Nara, & Wollmann, 2023; Lourenço, Gonçalves, Canciglieri Júnior, Dias, Benitez, Benitez, & Nara, 2024; Serra, Nara, Gonçalves, da Costa & Bortoluzzi, S.C., 2023; Serra, Gonçalves, Bortoluzzi, Costa, Dias, Benitez, Benitez & Nara, 2024;). Throughout the project development, several constraints and limitations were encountered. A strict delivery deadline and limited availability of resources were among the constraints. These factors posed

limitations on the project's freedom of action. Therefore, it was necessary to confine the project to a level of simplicity, always aiming to find the minimum viable solution to address the issue at hand.

It is suggested, as a proposal for future studies, to expand the application of the visual management tool to the job market area, targeting companies that use the competence-based model to select their candidates. The aim is to use the tool as a basis to produce a new interactive competency-based resume model. This will facilitate communication between candidates and companies, making it easier to identify the candidate's professional profile.

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